

DATA ANALYTICS MODEL IN LOAN APPROVAL PREDICTION**Norboev Bekhzod**

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Abstract: The goal of the project is to fully automate the loan approval prediction process. The dataset needs to be thoroughly examined. The diagram below illustrates the research process that was used for this project. The best models selected from the initial model evaluation process will be subjected to model-based feature selection.

Keywords: SPSS Modeler, SPSS Statistics, Data Modelling, CRISP-DM technique, Classification Methods, Classification Methods, Machine Learning (ML), Logistic Regression, Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs)

Environment

For this project, we have performed various modeling steps using the provided datasets and have identified key insights using SPSS Modeler and SPSS Statistics. We have analyzed exploratory data using SPSS Statistics, and we have completed the machine learning modeling stages using SPSS Modeler. Through data statistics summaries and visualization, the statistics tool has also assisted us in gaining various insights.

CRISP-DM Methodology Process

A process model known as CRISP-DM describes a six-phase sequential data science process. You can see them in figure 2.

Knowledge of Business

At this point in the process, the banking industry is fully understood, and pertinent cases pertaining to loan application and processing are examined in order to have a solid grasp of the subject and approach the issue with well-informed solution options.

Data Interpretation

In order to acquire a deeper understanding of the data, the dataset is gathered at this stage and put through statistical modeling and exploratory data analysis. The first stage is to examine and obtain a general understanding of the dataset, which includes assessing the continuous characteristics' mean values and standard deviation.

Data Gathering

The dataset must be thoroughly examined and cleaned of any missing values after this. This stage helps to guarantee the accuracy of the analysis by finding missing values and data types for every feature. Cleaning the data on these problems is important since, for example, it can lead to biased conclusions if the response column has missing values from typos.

Data Modelling

The dataset is used to create a machine learning model and train the data after being cleaned. As a result, in the last phase, outcome values can be predicted. To prepare the training and test sets, which enable training and assessing the accuracy of the clustering results, it is essential to comprehend the features in the dataset.

Assessment

Validating the created model and assessing the clusters' quality comprise the last phase. To prevent any misunderstanding of the outcomes, it's critical to evaluate if the values in the clusters are significant and consistent with expectations.

Following the sequential phases in the CRISP-DM technique gives accurate conclusions and recommendations for stakeholders while offering a systematic approach to problem solving. This kind of procedure guarantees a project that is well-planned and works toward the intended results.

The CRISP-DM approach was applied in this project to investigate and identify the optimal model for loan processing and application in the banking sector. After obtaining the dataset from Kaggle, missing values and outliers were eliminated to prepare it for analysis and machine learning. Ultimately, parameters including accuracy, gain, and AUC were used to assess the model performance, and the best-fit model was chosen to predict loan applications based on creditworthiness and additional variables.

Classification Methods

A data-mining technique called classification separates a set of data into groups to facilitate analysis and forecasting. With a given set of inputs, classification models will attempt to predict the value of one or more outputs. The study's findings include labels for debt statuses of 1 or 0. Loan applications might be approved or denied based on machine learning algorithms.

Models for machine learning

The two primary types of machine learning are supervised and unsupervised learning.

Using labeled datasets, supervised learning improves an algorithm's capacity for data recognition and precise result prediction. In Figure 1, the idea of supervised learning is displayed.

Figure 1 - Supervised Learning Process

Unsupervised learning is required when there is simply input data and no associated output variables or labels. The concept of unsupervised learning is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 - Unsupervised Learning process

The model in this study was trained on datasets that had labels. Consequently, rather than using unsupervised learning models, supervised learning models were used. supervised learning classification models include Support Vector Machine, Multinomial Naive Bayes, Decision Tree, Random Forest, Logistic Regression, and XGBoost. The free and open-source Python sklearn framework is used to create these models for approving or rejecting loan applications.

Logistic Regression

Logistic regression is a widely used and fundamental method for binary classification in machine learning. Using logistic regression, the link between one dependent binary variable and independent factors is explained and estimated. In particular, this kind of linear regression happens when the target variable is categorical in nature.[1] The logistic sigmoid function generates a probability value that can be applied to two or more discrete groups based on the outcomes of the logistic regression. Any real number can be converted using the sigmoid function into a value between 0 and 1.

Linear regression equation:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_n X_n \quad (1)$$

Sigmoid Function:

$$p = \frac{1}{1+e^{-y}} \quad (2)$$

Apply Sigmoid function on linear regression:

$$p = \frac{1}{1+e^{-\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_n X_n}} \quad (3)$$

Logistic Regression Equation:

$$\log\left(\frac{p}{1-p}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_n X_n \quad (4)$$

Where, y : Response variable

p : Probability of response class

β_i : Regression coefficients

X_n : Predictor variables

The greatest likelihood technique is used to estimate the values of these coefficients. For binary logistic regression, the dependent variable needs to be dichotomous, the data needs to be independent, and there shouldn't be any anomalies.

This classifier outperforms some of the more complex machine learning models when conditional independence is satisfied. It is functioning about as effectively while dealing with categorical data as opposed to numerical data. Numerous Naive Bayes models, including MultinomialNB, GaussianNB, ComplementNB, BernoulliNB, and

CategoricalNB, are included in the scikit-learn package. The Naive Bayes model produces erroneous probability outputs because it is a poor estimator despite being an effective classifier[2].

The purpose of this section is to provide an explanation of the models that will be utilized in the upcoming portions of the modeling phase. Before we move forward with the task's practicality, it is imperative that we gain a deeper understanding of the candidate models and the performance KPIs that are associated with them. We employ a number of models using SPSS Modeler in this experiment, including Random Trees, Neural Networks, Decision Trees, Logistic Regression, and C5. Each of the models has a brief description mentioned below.

Random Trees.

The ensemble learning technique Random Forest is an effective way to tackle problems related to regression and classification. It is renowned for its strong scoring methods and makes predictions using a collection of decision trees. Numerous research investigations have verified this strategy, which consistently produces good performance results[3].

C5.

This derives a prediction strategy using either a rule set or a decision tree. Iteratively, this strategy of repeatedly splitting the tree is used[4]. With the addition of a layer of rules to carry out the process in an organized way, this modeling procedure is an expanded version of the decision tree modeling procedure.

Network Neural 1

A kind of machine learning method called Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) is based on the composition and operations of the human brain. With the help of a network of linked nodes that includes input, hidden, and output layers, this method processes input information and generates predictions based on the correlations between them. By taking into account the interactions between input nodes, hidden layers, and output nodes, the ANN model can make complex decisions. In the end, it

produces outputs that are indicative of the data that is transferred through the network[5].

Conclusion

The key research question is to create an autonomous smart loan approval system that will use machine learning techniques to approve or deny loan applications. The study made use of machine learning models with varying degrees of complexity. Linear models, tree-based models, boosting models, voting models, and stacking models are all included in this category.

The goal of this study is to identify the major parameters influencing loan approval, investigate the correlations between these predictor variables and loan approval outcomes, and develop a machine learning model to predict loan approval for clients. Customers and the company will profit from this because it will provide insights before the model is implemented. The primary chapter describes the fundamental value as well as the technique in detail.

Literature

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